

THE AUTHOR'S SKILL IN DESCRIBING THE CHARACTER OF THE SERVANT IN THE NOVELS OF ABDULLA KADIRI AND OYBEK

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Abstract. This article analyzes the concept of servants in the novels of Abdulla Kadiri and Oybek. The ways of description of servants take place in this article. Although these two writers lived and wrote novels in the same period, we can witness diversity on their works while describing servants.

Key words. Poetics, speech, image, qualification, exaggeration, plot, metaphor, emotionality, character

Introduction. Oybek's writing career began with poetry. In the 1920s and 1930s Oybek became known for his prose works, in which the writer was able to demonstrate the lyrical elation, high poetic mood, and passionate feelings. Various aspects of Oybek's writing style have been studied by Uzbek scholars. Oybek is a skilled writer who describes the portraits of heroes in both poetry and prose, eye and eyebrow movements very clearly, and Oybek is a psychologist who can get into a person's heart.

Main part. In the first major prose work of the writer "Holy Blood" novel, the writer created a poetic, beautiful and unique image style like no other. The author's speech in the novel "Holy Blood" is distinguished by its closeness to figurative, poetic speech, that is, the use of poetic tools such as simile, metaphor, qualification, exaggeration, allusion, etc. These characteristics of Oybek's style are:

a) describing the landscape; b) drawing a portrait of a hero; c) expressing the inner world of the characters; g) clearly manifested in providing high emotionality in the artistic image¹. Oybek's artistic depiction of reality differs from Abdulla Kadiri's artistic depiction style, for example, Abdulla Kadiri begins his works by first introducing his hero, then describing the environment in which these heroes enter and are expected to improve. An example of this is the complete image of the servant Hasanali in the first pages of Kadiri's "Bygone Days". And Oybek first describes the conditions in which the hero enters and is formed, the space and time around the hero, the environment and other characters in it move. For example, Oybek did not describe the image of the servant Yormat in the novel "Holy Blood" at the beginning of the work. In this novel, the method of contrasting images is used to form the character of the hero and reflect the situation with all its contradictions. A large number of details and heroes are characteristic for the work of Abdulla Kadiri and Oybek.

All the used details are necessary for the authors to correctly and convincingly show the leading qualities of the hero's nature, his position and situation in life, and to describe the conditions historically. For example, if we pay attention to the details in the image of Yormat: *"Yormat took out several rice baskets from the table, a steaming round of pilaf, etc. The cart is full. Yormat decorated every part of the carriage and then quickly mounted the horse. He sat hunched and hunched like a new, "amateur" teenage stroller. Then, while whipping the horse, he yelled at Yolchi. (page 18)*

Abdulla Kadiri uses details to reveal the hero's character more deeply, to exaggerate the most important aspects, to determine how and who he is, while Oybek uses it to ensure the dynamics of the hero's character.

¹ N.Karimov. XX asr o'zbek adabiyoti tarixi. Darslik. T., "O'qituvchi", 1999. 215-b. 139

For example, "Yormat sprinkled a lot of water on the cart with a bucket. Then he swept it well. He put on the horse tools with shells, mowed the path with red rags, went around the horse and gave it a lot of beauty. After preparing the horse, he put thick felt on the cart and spread a blanket over it. His every move showed that he was trying to prepare a place as comfortable as possible for the women. He must have liked very much to carry the owners' wives and children in a cart to lavish hospitality, so he was proud and happy now. But he doesn't express his happiness, even his frown looks more serious. Yulchi laughed at the "childish nature" of this man because he tried his tricks to some degree. When the cart was ready, Yormat ran away as if forgetting something important. He made a small ladder from somewhere and got on the back of the cart. He put his arm around his waist and knocks here himself." (p. 18) As it can be seen from the example, Yormat tries very hard to win the trust of his master, his childish character and qualities such as boasting and haste are manifested in his various actions.

From the first pages of the novel "Holy blood", Oybek describes different aspects of the characters of Yolchi and Yormat, two hard-working representatives of the Uzbek people, who were later servants in the Mirzakarimboy household. He writes about Yulchi's poor youth, the fact that when he couldn't find a job in the village, he came to his uncle in the city, and that "great courage and pride can be felt in his whole figure." Yormat, like Yulchi, is a poor man, but he is loyal to the rich family he serves, "a proud poor man whose whole stature and every effort he has given to himself," the author has beautifully described.

Conclusion. In Oybek's novel "Holy blood", different aspects of the characters of Yulchi and Yormat, who were servants in Mirzakarimboy's household, are analyzed, and it can be observed that they and other laborers served their master faithfully for years without agreeing to pay. Thousands of types of servants are described in the work: horsemen, carters, laborers, slaves, peasants, hired farmers, etc.

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